

Additive Manufacturing in Atomic Layer Processing Mode

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Additive manufacturing (3D printing) has not been applicable to micro- and nanoscale engineering due to the limited resolution. Atomic layer deposition (ALD) is a technique for coating large areas with atomic thickness resolution based on tailored surface chemical reactions. Thus, combining the principles of additive manufacturing with ALD could open up a completely new field of manufacturing. Indeed, it is shown that a spatially localized delivery of ALD precursors can generate materials patterns. In this “atomic-layer additive manufacturing” (ALAM), the vertical resolution of the solid structure deposited is about 0.1 nm, whereas the lateral resolution is defined by the microfluidic gas delivery. The ALAM principle is demonstrated by generating lines and patterns of pure, crystalline TiO₂ and Pt on planar substrates and conformal coatings of 3D nanostructures. The functional quality of ALAM patterns is exemplified with temperature sensors, which achieve a performance similar to the industry standard. This general method of multimaterial direct patterning is much simpler than standard multistep lithographic microfabrication. It offers process flexibility, saves processing time, investment, materials, waste, and energy. It is envisioned that together with etching, doping, and cleaning performed in a similar local manner, ALAM will create the “atomic-layer advanced manufacturing” family of techniques.

are generated by a repetitive sequence of processing steps in which for each material a sacrificial resist layer is deposited, then patterned, then used to transfer its pattern into the desired material layer, and finally removed. This framework does not allow for the direct deposition of a patterned functional material. Its reliance on a small number of sacrificial “resists” and the multiple removal and cleaning steps cause large amounts of material waste. It also requires significant resources of energy, processing time, and facility investment. Additionally, lithography-based fabrication is highly suitable to the generation of identical products in large numbers, but it does not offer prompt access and flexibility to prototyping individual devices. In the manufacturing of large parts, prototyping has been rendered increasingly accessible using additive manufacturing (3D printing) strategies.^[4–8] Here, the functional material is directly deposited in patterned form using various strategies such as miniaturized nozzles and laser or electron beams. However, so far the resolution (the smallest feature size controllable)

1. Introduction

The semiconductor industry is a highly successful economic sector, the growth of which has been based for the past 60 years on the powerful combination of two families of techniques: thin film depositions and lithographic patterning.^[1–3] Functional devices

has been on the order of hundreds of micrometers, although the integration of nanostructures into 3D-printed materials or patterns is possible.^[9–18] In other words, 3D printing is several orders of magnitude away from the feature sizes accessible by lithographic methods. In summary, 3D printing has the direct pattern generation capability and materials versatility, whereas

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Figure 1. a) Microfluidic precursor delivery concept: Schematic view of the delivery nozzle in frontal view (top) and in cross-section (lower panel). b) Demonstration of direct pattern generation by ALAM: Pt-printed ATLANT logo featuring letters from A to T obtained with 140, 150, 170, 190, 200, and 210 individual passes, respectively. Top panel, imaging spectroscopic ellipsometry map of the Pt thickness on a linear scale. Lower panel, low-energy ion scattering spectroscopy map presented on a logarithmic scale, yielding the element composition of the top atomic layer.

lithography has the resolution. Combining the advantages of both has not been possible so far.

We have achieved this desirable combination by performing atomic layer deposition (ALD) from a miniaturized gas delivery nozzle and established the characteristics of what we call atomic-layer additive manufacturing (ALAM). The thin coating method ALD relies on an alternation of complementary, self-termination gas-solid surface reactions, each of which results in film thickness increases by Angström amounts and that are repeated in a cyclic manner until the goal thickness is reached.^[19,20] Although the alternation between delivery of the two distinct gaseous precursors is often defined in time, it can also be defined in space. In this case, the substrate is usually shuttled between spatially separate volumes of influence of “precursor A” and “precursor B”. The spatial strategy has mostly been pursued with the goal of achieving the highest possible homogeneities over large coating areas.^[21–27] Here, the opposite trend will be pursued: we will confine the precursor gas flows laterally as much as possible.

We note the recent successes and advances of area-selective deposition (ASD) as a method in which ALD is used to deposit only on specific surfaces, as opposed to a full, continuous layer.^[28,29] This approach, however, does not generate its own pattern, it only reproduces a pattern preliminarily defined on the substrate. Atomic-layer 3D printing can be achieved by performing thin film deposition in a highly localized manner. Conceptually, the thickness control of the deposition technique could provide the vertical resolution whereas a lateral localization would determine the horizontal resolution. Two recent first forays in this direction have been proposed. The first exploits a localized plasma as one ALD precursor, whereas the other precursor is not spatially resolved.^[30] This has allowed for the definition of 1 cm wide lines with true ALD control of growth, but is limited to plasma-based chemistry. The other delivers both ALD precursors in close proximity to one another and has generated centimeter-wide lines,^[31] yet an experimental demonstration of ALD growth control is yet to be provided.

2. Results and Discussion

In the following, we will describe true direct patterning deposition with sub-millimeter line width based on the localization of precursor A and B deliveries in a miniaturized nozzle, accompanied by a motion of the sample under the delivery head. For this purpose of performing ALD chemistry in a highly localized manner, we implement the principle of the A/vacuum/inert gas/B/vacuum pattern in a miniaturized concentric nozzle, **Figure 1a**.^[32] The nozzle is a monolithic part on the face of which the “precursor A” outlet is placed centrally and can have a diameter of 80 μm (standard) or 20 μm (advanced version). The concentric rings arranged around it apply vacuum, deliver argon, then deliver precursor B and finally apply vacuum, respectively. In this manner, the gas streams of precursors A and B are directed towards the closest source of vacuum and the inert gas ensures their spatial separation. The inner ring of vacuum exhaust opening has a diameter of 400 μm or 120 μm and the “precursor B” ring 1000 μm or 1160 μm (in standard and advanced versions, respectively). When the face of the nozzle is situated at a small distance from a substrate, each precursor flows from its outlet to the vacuum line over the substrate surface. The substrate surface is therefore exposed to each precursor locally. Motions of the substrate under the nozzle therefore result in consecutive exposures of any given point to A and B subsequently. The gap between nozzle face and substrate is maintained at a value $\approx 125\%$ of the diameter of the precursor A outlet by a machined kinematic system. We have observed that changes in this distance by $\pm 20\%$ of the nominal value maintain the fluid dynamic constraints and therefore result in no changes in the deposition characteristics. The sample is heated by direct contact with a heating plate placed between it and the motion control stage.

Let us start with the deposition of metallic platinum from the known ALD reaction between (methylcyclopentadienyl)platinum trimethyl ((MeCp)PtMe₃) and ozone (O₃) at 250 °C.^[33–36] The organometallic precursor (MeCp)PtMe₃ is delivered via the central nozzle opening whereas O₃ is provided from the

external circle. The top panel of Figure 1b presents the results obtained when a pattern of short, angled lines is generated using alternating motions of the substrate (under the standard microfluidic precursor delivery nozzle). One obtains lines the (vertical) thickness of which increases linearly with the number of passes, from ≈ 14 nm for 140 individual passes of the nozzle to 20 nm for 200 passes (as determined by imaging ellipsometry, Figure 1b top panel).

The lateral width of the line is determined neither by the diameter of the central “precursor A” delivery outlet nor by that of the external “precursor B” delivery outlet. Instead, it reflects the width of the zone exposed to precursor A at each pass (each point exposed to A being inherently also exposed to B subsequently). This zone corresponds to the diameter of the ring on which the vacuum inlets are placed: 400 μm with the standard nozzle (Figure 1) and 150 μm with the advanced nozzle (Figure S1a, Supporting Information). The bulk of each line experiences two full ALD cycles when the nozzle performs one full alternating motion, but the cylindrical arrangement of the gas delivery nozzle causes an artefact near the line extremities. Indeed, any point too close to the precursor A outlet does not experience exposure to B before being exposed to A a second time. This effect generates line extremities with a segment of half the bulk line thickness. Conversely, areas at crossings of two lines exhibit double the thickness.

An elemental mapping by low-energy ion scattering (LEIS) is used to analyze trace contamination of the substrate in areas nominally not exposed to the ALD precursors (lower panel of Figure 1b presented on a logarithmic scale). Indeed, the extreme sensitivity of LEIS in the uppermost surface layer of the sample enables the detection of very low amounts of adventitious Pt deposit. The quantitative analysis near the left extremity of the pattern yields a composition of 100% Pt on the line and less than 0.3% Pt beside it. In other words, one has a 14-nm thick line next to a background contaminated to less than nominally 0.0006 nm—a selectivity on the order of 10^5 . The distance between the nozzle and the substrate was increased from left to right of Figure 1b until it became too large to ensure perfect lateral constraint and spatial separation of the precursor gases. The LEIS analysis demonstrates the onset of uncontrolled mixing between precursors A and B (right extremity of Figure 1b, lower panel), with 5% surface coverage with Pt present in nominally unexposed areas (an areal selectivity reduced to $\approx 10^4$). Taken together, these results demonstrate the successful spatial separation of the two distinct ALD precursors and the perfection of the contrast between exposed and unexposed areas. This perfection results from the digital nature of the ALD chemistry on which the ALAM process relies.

Indeed, ALD chemistry is defined by the repetition of two complementary surface reactions each of which is self-limiting. This self-limiting property results from the saturation of surface reactive groups with incoming precursor, and it generates a growth mode in which the amount (thickness) of solid deposited is independent on the amount (partial pressure) of precursor provided in the gas phase.^[19,20] One can describe the deposition as having a digital nature. Classically, the ALD growth mode is demonstrated experimentally by (1) a linear increase of deposit thickness with number of ALD cycle repeats

and (2) the absence of growth rate dependence on either quantitative precursor exposure or process temperature. Figure 2 provides this demonstration for two individual ALD reactions for the particular case of ALAM. In addition to the Pt reaction used in the previous paragraph, we add the characteristics obtained for a completely different, but also classic, ALD reaction, namely the one between titanium tetrakis(isopropoxide) ($\text{Ti}(\text{O}^i\text{Pr})_4$) and water (H_2O) to TiO_2 at 150 °C.^[37,38] In Figure 2a, the growth “rates” (in units of thickness growth per cycle or per pass) are determined as the slopes of the growth curves (measured by ellipsometry). The TiO_2 ALAM process exhibits linear growth at 0.35 Å per pass, consistent with the ALD literature.^[39] The Pt growth is not perfectly linear as a result of the nucleation inhibition that is well documented in the ALD literature.^[37] The average growth rate determined after 400 passes is 0.09 Å per pass, also in line with expectations.

These growth curves are no unambiguous proof of the ALD growth mode. The definitive proof of self-limiting surface chemistry is delivered by a variation of precursor dosage and/or temperature, which should not influence growth rate (over a certain range). For the present case, the precursor dosage is varied by the gas flow rate delivered to the nozzle, which exhibits flat lines within the processing parameter window (Figure 2c). Furthermore, the temperature can be varied over a rather large window (from 120 to 260 °C for TiO_2 and from 200 to 250 °C for Pt) without any massive growth rate variation (Figure 2d). Additionally, the spatially constrained ALAM allows for the interrogation of the lateral thickness profile as an additional tool to characterize the underlying ALD surface chemistry. A deposition method not defined by self-limiting surface reactions (such as chemical vapor deposition or molecular beam deposition) would deliver an approximately Gaussian thickness profile if precursors were delivered locally. The results presented in Figure 2b exhibit the horizontal plateau and the sharp edges expected to result from the digital nature of ALD and ALAM surface chemistry. The exact edge characterization performed by atomic force microscopy (AFM) yields a sloped section of ≈ 7 μm width (Figure S2, Supporting Information).

The functional performance of any device generated by ALAM will depend on the chemical and structural quality of the solid deposited. Figure 3 displays the analytical results collected on our ALAM-Pt. The solid lines (Figure 3a) consist of metallic platinum, as indicated by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS, Figure 3c). The X-ray diffractogram (XRD, Figure 3b) demonstrates the crystalline nature of the material, which is confirmed by transmission electron microscopy (TEM, Figure 3d–f). High-resolution TEM and selected-area electron diffraction (SAED, Figure 3f) highlight the size of individual crystals (larger than 100 nm and the thickness of the layer) and their excellent quality.

Not only can ALAM generate line patterns, the underlying principles of ALD inherently provide the capability to create more complex structures on various substrates. First, lines can be combined in a rastering motion to generate wider planar areas (Figure S1b, Supporting Information), whereby the areas of influence of “precursor B” can overlap without consequence for the amount deposited (without resulting in line overlaps featuring double thickness). The reproducibility and homogeneity are excellent over large sample areas (Figure S1c, Supporting

Figure 2. Characterization of self-limiting surface chemistry and digital growth in ALAM. Thicknesses are determined for two distinct ALAM materials by ellipsometry. a) Increase of deposit thickness with number of passes. b) Deposit line height profiles after various pass numbers, demonstrating maintained line width and edge sharpness. c) Demonstration of the self-limiting characteristic of the surface reactions by varying precursor dosage in the form of either gas flow rate or sample motion speed. d) Dependence of the growth rate (determined from a linear growth curve) on the substrate temperature, demonstrating the presence of an "ALD window".

Information). We note that some line imperfections observable in Figure 1b and Figure S1 (Supporting Information) are caused by step defects of the motion stage used here, which has a 5 μm step size in x and y . The pattern uniformity will be improved upon use of a direct-drive stage with a smaller steps and true circular/diagonal motions. Secondly, the self-limiting surface chemistry allows ALAM to coat non-planar substrates in a conformal manner. The micrographs presented in Figure 4 at various levels of magnification, with various substrates and with the two distinct ALAM materials TiO₂ and Pt demonstrate the generality of this statement. Porosity on the nanoscale does not affect the sharp edges of lines on the micron scale. Each individual pore or trench is coated in a conformal manner. The thickness deposited is identical on the top and bottom surfaces of trenches as well as on their vertical walls. These data demonstrate the generality and versatility of direct pattern generation by ALAM.

A proof of the high structural and chemical quality of the materials deposited by ALAM is provided by a set of demonstrator devices built using it. Figure 5 presents the perfor-

mance of various ALAM-defined Pt lines as resistive temperature sensors. Both the deposition temperature and the line thickness can be varied as adjustable parameters (the former is presented in black, red and blue colors; the latter is the abscissa of Figure 5b,c and appears with the dotted line in Figure 5a). Here, the devices have been designed to exhibit resistances on the same order of magnitude as the one chosen as the industry standard (100 Ω in the "Pt100") and as a reference processed by classical PVD/lithography methods (green, Figure 5a). The absolute resistance is easily adjustable based on the line thickness and it depends on temperature linearly. The temperature sensitivities S are comparable to those exhibited by the PVD control (same geometry) and by the Pt100 (of macroscopic size, Figure 5b). The temperature coefficients of resistance (Figure 5c) are mostly situated between those of PVD device and Pt100. In other words, the first ALAM devices made perform on the level of state-of-the-art devices prepared with more complex processing procedures.

Figure 3. Materials characterization of ALAM-Pt. a) Scanning electron micrograph of two Pt lines. b) Grazing-incidence X-ray diffraction exhibiting the peaks expected of microcrystalline, metallic Pt. c) X-ray photoelectron spectrum recorded near the Pt 4f edge displaying a perfect spin-orbit split $4f_{7/2}/4f_{5/2}$ doublet, demonstrating chemical purity. d–f) Transmission electron micrographs of a Pt line investigated in cross-section at three different magnification levels. The high-resolution data allow one to observe the presence of large (>100 nm) individual crystals oriented with the [112] direction perpendicular to the substrate surface. The inset shows the selected-area electron diffraction pattern obtained from one single crystal.

3. Discussion and Conclusions

Confining the delivery of gaseous reactive precursors in space allows one to combine the flexibility and power of additive

manufacturing (3D printing) with the atomic resolution inherent to ALD processing.

From the perspective of the 3D printing field, the extreme (and even absolute) vertical resolution of Å achievable is more

Figure 4. Excerpt of morphologies enabled by ALAM on non-planar substrates, observed in scanning electron microscopy. a) “Anodic” aluminum oxide macropores coated with Pt: the roughness of Pt nuclei is clearly visible and homogeneous along the pore length. b) Nanostructured black Si surface coated with 20/300/600/1000 ALAM Pt passes (combination of separate micrographs). c) Cross-section of a Si trench coated with a Pt layer (high magnification). d) Top view of aligned Si trenches (aligned horizontally) coated with a perpendicular line of TiO_2 (low magnification SEM).

Figure 5. Performance of a set of ALAM demonstrator devices as compared with the industry standard and with a reference obtained from classical physical deposition and lithographic processing: temperature sensors. a) Electrical resistance of lines deposited with 200 ALAM passes at three different temperatures; a line deposited with 500 ALAM passes at 200 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and one deposited by electron-beam evaporation (PVD, 30 nm) are presented for comparison in dotted gray and in green lines, respectively. b) Temperature sensitivity $S = \Delta R/\Delta T$ of the various devices as compared with the PVD reference (green datapoint) and with the macroscopically sized Pt100 industry standard (orange line). c) Temperature coefficient of resistance $\alpha = S/R_0$ of the same devices: ALAM devices approach the performance of Pt100 and are mostly superior to the PVD-processed reference (of thickness similar to 400 ALAM passes).

than just an exciting advance, it represents a quantum leap. The lateral line width on the scale of $>100\ \mu\text{m}$ does not stem from a fundamental limitation but a technical one. We do not see any fundamental reason why scaling the microfluidic system down to $10\ \mu\text{m}$ lateral feature size should become problematic. Reaching these line widths will be a matter of generating gas delivery features of sizes on the order of individual microns arranged in 3Ds within the monolithic gas delivery nozzle and of controlling the sample to nozzle gap accordingly, which is technically challenging but certainly possible. From the perspective of the ALD community, and of the semiconductor and MEMS/NEMS industrial applications, ALAM represents the first direct pattern generation in atomic scale processing. In classical semiconductor processing, despite the steady advances in lithographic feature-size shrinking over the past 60 years, each of many layers is blanket-deposited and only then patterned and etched, requiring additional process steps and leaving significant waste. With ALAM, in contrast to this, the functional materials are obtained directly in their patterned form and in high quality. Several distinct materials can even be combined with each other in order to create structures that are limited neither to two-dimensional patterns nor to aligned stacks (as they are in area-selective deposition),^[28,29] but which may exhibit overlaps and exploit the full design flexibility of true three-dimensional design instead, with sub-nanometer control on the z axis (Figure S3, Supporting Information). Devices made with ALAM can achieve a performance on par with those generated by established methods. The excellent adhesion of ALD films, which has been demonstrated and is due to the chemical nature of nucleation on the substrate,^[40–43] will remain valid for ALAM features and provides an additional advantage.

Is this achievement unprecedented? Electron beam-induced deposition (EBID) does allow for the generation of three-dimensional nanoscale geometries of functional materials.^[44–45] However, it is limited to a very small number of materials. In contrast to this, ALAM can exploit the wide range of ALD materials established, which includes oxides (such as high-quality dielectrics and barrier materials), metals (catalysts, electrical conductors), heavy chalcogenides (light absorbers,

semiconductors, and electroluminescent sources), and hybrids (metalorganics).^[20] In a different vein, selected-area atomic layer deposition does yield a coating on designated areas only, but the pattern must be generated in a preliminary step. Therefore, ALAM is the only technology that delivers direct patterning with materials versatility, substrate chemical flexibility, conformality on structured substrates, and atomic resolution simultaneously. Further practical advantages include the fast processing ability (cycle times on the order of individual milliseconds), the low precursor consumption and waste generation, and the atmospheric conditions of processing. Further developments will generalize the principles of ALAM to atomic-layer etching and to multi-nozzle, multimaterial printing. Together, this family of techniques performing addition and subtraction of material with atomic precision vertically and within microfluidic constraints laterally could be called atomic-layer advanced manufacturing.

4. Experimental Section

Chemicals were purchased from abcr, Alfa Aesar, Sigma–Aldrich, and VWR and used as received. Si (100) wafers covered with a thermal oxide layer were supplied by Silicon Materials Inc. Water was purified in a Millipore Direct-Q system. Ozone was generated with a BMT 803N ozone generator from oxygen purchased from Air Liquide.

The reaction volume was defined as the region of space enclosed by the gas outlet of the nozzle and the substrate. The depositions were carried out in a home-built pressure flow reactor operating at atmospheric pressure. The precursors were $(\text{MeCp})\text{PtMe}_3$ and ozone (from an ozone generator using oxygen as a source at 0.5 bar overpressure) for Pt deposition, and $(\text{PrO})_4\text{Ti}$ and water for titania (precursor source temperatures: 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, room temperature, 70 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, and room temperature, respectively). Precursor vapors were transferred to the nozzle with argon as the carrier gas set to a flow rate of 25 sccm, via lines heated to 90 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Pt) or 80 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (TiO_2). The nozzle temperature was kept at 100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Pt) or 120 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (TiO_2). Water and ozone supply were set by an increase of 1.5 mbar in the back pressure. The substrate holder temperature was varied between 120 and 300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ as described in the main text. Sample and nozzle were optically aligned by the experimentalist. As delivered by the nozzle, precursors, and vacuum (17–23 mbar) were spatially separated by a purge flow of argon and supplied in a continuous manner. Patterns were defined by moving the

sample stage with respect to the gas delivery nozzle. Stage control is provided by XILabs.

Ellipsometry contrast images with lateral resolution were provided by an EP4 ellipsometer equipped with a DCC camera (Accurion GmbH, Germany). High sensitivity LEIS measurements were carried out with a 5-keV beam of $^{20}\text{Ne}^+$ in a Qtac100 instrument equipped with a time-of-flight mass filter (IONTOF GmbH, Germany). Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) spectra were obtained with a Jeol JSM 6400 upgraded with a LaB_6 cathode and SDD X-ray detector. The crystal structure of the samples was identified by Grazing-incidence X-ray diffraction (GIXRD) with $\text{Cu K}\alpha 1$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.54056 \text{ \AA}$) on a Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer equipped with a LynxEye XE-T detector. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was carried out with a monochromatized $\text{Al K}\alpha$ X-ray source (PHI Quantera II, Japan). Atomic force microscopy (AFM) images are obtained with a Veeco Dimension 3100 microscope using tapping mode. Silicon probe tips from Bruker were used with a spring constant of 2 N m^{-1} and resonance frequency 70 kHz.

The cross-section sample for transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was prepared with a focused ion beam instrument FEI Helios NanoLab 660. The TEM investigation was performed at 300 kV using a FEI Titan³ Themis 300 microscope equipped with an ultra-bright X-FEG electron source and spherical aberration correctors on both probe-forming and imaging side.

The PVD sensor structures were fabricated on Si substrates covered with 300 nm thick thermal SiO_2 , by first coating and patterning the photoresist using photolithography, leaving the areas of desired deposition open. Subsequently, Pt was deposited using electron beam evaporation with the substrate temperature kept at $70 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The remaining Pt-coated photoresist was then removed in acetone using ultrasonic bath (lift-off procedure) leaving only the desired Pt pattern on the substrate. Both types of sensor structures were contacted by Au pads placed at a defined distance from each other, using similar PVD procedures. All sensors were annealed for 30 min at $600 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in N_2 ambient to ensure thermal stability. The sensors' R - T characteristics were measured in the range of 25 to $400 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ multiple times each. All the sensors' TCR values were calculated as sensitivity normalized by their room-temperature resistance.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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